

NOTES

Chemical Examination of *Litchi chinensis* Sonner Syn.

Nephelium litchi Camb.

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Litchi chinensis (Sapindaceae) is widely cultivated in India. The leaves of the plant are reported to be useful as a cure for bites of animals¹. The investigations on the stem bark of the above plant and the isolation of friedelin and stigmasterol are reported in the present communication.

Dried and powdered bark (1 kg.) of *L. chinensis* was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) in a soxhlet apparatus for 12 hrs. The crude residue (11 g.), left after the evaporation of solvent, was separated into neutral (9 g.) and acidic (1.5 g.) parts by the usual procedure. The latter after chromatography over silica gel did not yield any crystalline material. The neutral part (9 g.), in turn, on chromatography over deactivated alumina (150 g.) and elution with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) yielded a gummy solid (0.72 g.), which on rechromatography and crystallisation from petroleum ether gave a solid (0.06 g.), m.p. 252–55°, $(\alpha)_D - 19.7^\circ$ (CHCl₃) which was identified as friedelin by colour test and mixed m.p.

Further elution of the column with a mixture of petroleum ether and benzene (3 : 2) gave a gummy solid (1.18 g.), which on rechromatography followed by crystallisation yielded a solid (0.1 g.), m.p. 153–57°. Liebermann-Burchard reaction showed a positive test for sterol. Acetylation of the above solid (0.3 g.) with acetic anhydride (3 ml.) and pyridine (3 ml.), yielded a crude acetate which on crystallisation from methanol, gave the pure acetate (0.1 g.), m.p. 137–39°. The sterol and the acetate were identified (mixed m.p.) as stigmasterol and stigmasteryl acetate respectively.

Benzene extraction of the above defatted plant material and chromatography of the crude residue, left after solvent evaporation, yielded only gummy matter.

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1. R. N. Chopra, S. L. Nayar and I. C. Chopra, 'Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants,' (Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi), 1956, 155.
2. K. Paech and M. V. Tracey, 'Modern Methods of Plant Analysis, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1955, 3, 64.